

USE OF WEB-QUEST TECHNOLOGY IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING ENGLISH

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In accordance with the language policy of our country, English is priority foreign language to be studied at all educational institutions. Therefore, in Prosperous Epoch of “Happy Youth with Arkadag Serdar”, fluent of English has become the major requirement for high quality education. It’s especially true for our university since English is medium of instruction over here.

One of the challenges of modern education is to enhance the variety of types and forms pedagogical educational system, such activities allow significantly increase educational opportunities, to make a choice and implementation of individual trajectories of open educational space. XXI century requires new approaches to education.

Information Technology helps to create a new educational surrounding in which students are involved and able to accept more responsibility for their own training and designing them own knowledge. Certain experience on the use of Internet resources have already been accumulated by teachers in the self-organization of students. Firstly this is the usage of Internet at implementation of individual or group research work. It’s the way to integrate the Internet into foreign language teaching named – web quest. A web-quest in pedagogy means a problematic task with elements of a role – playing game, for fulfilment which is used for informational resources. Web-quest is difficult to students as well as to teachers. Web quest is directed to develop the analytical and creative thinking of learners. Teacher who is creating the web quest must have high level of methodical and into communication competence. Features of web quests is that some of the information or all of it for individual or group students, can be found in different sites. Web quests can cover both a single problem, a subject, a topic or can be interdisciplinary. B.Dodge highlights 3 web quest classification principles [1]:

1. By duration of fulfilment: long-term, short- ter.
2. Subject-wise content: mono projects and interdisciplinary web quests.
3. By the type of tasks performed by students: retelling tasks, complication tasks, riddles, journalistic tasks, design tasks, creative product, consensus building tasks, persuasive tasks, self- knowledge, analytical, evaluation, scientific tasks.

Web quest must have the following structure [1]:

1. Introduction (wording topics, description, major roles participants, scenario quest, an overview of the entire quest).
2. Central task (questions to which students must find the answer in framework, independent research, final result is to be achieved).
3. List of informational resources (the funds that can be used at implementation assignments).
4. Description of the main stages of work, management to actions.

Conclusion (results of research, questions for further development of the topic). In language learning can be used web quests such as [2]:

- Various educational discipline created for native speakers.
- For students of foreign languages.

Using web quest and other resource-based tasks on Internet requires from students language skills for authentic resources. In connection with this effective integration you can learn languages through web quest when:

- It's creative task completing the study of a topic.
- Accompanied training and lexical grammar based on exercises web quest's authentic resources. Such exercises can either precede work on the quest or be carried out in parallel with it. Topics for web quests can be the most diverse, problematic tasks can vary in degree of difficulty.

Results of complete web quests, independent from the studied material, can be presented in the form of an oral presentation, computer presentation essay, web page etc.

Advantages [2]:

1. Web quests give a teacher a clear model of how to conduct project work.
2. Model of working. Quests use a lot with web teachers in various countries, so you can find many interesting developments.
3. Online available templates that can be very useful for teachers to create their own web quests, a lot of methodological advice for teachers.
4. Teachers provide a list of sites which students use when completing a project.
5. One of the important reasons why should we use web technology is that many students will work to improve level of proficiency.

Difficulties and problems. In reality, of course, the picture isn't so rosy and there are many difficulties [3]:

1. To complete the project students must have access to Net.
2. Web-quest technology from children and adults require a level of computer literacy certain slow Internet may limit the type of uploaded sources (video materials).

Web-quests are being used a long time ago and have a clear structure. However it is not something that may be frozen and used only as a base which can be changed. The quest is divided into 4 main sections: introduction, assignment, execution, evaluation. Technology web quest has a universal character and can be used for purposes such as development competence in the field of independent cognitive activities based on the assimilation of methods of acquiring knowledge shells. Technology can stimulate the cognitive activity of students, as it's new, and allows not only to students but teachers also to express creative personality which is essential in modern educational process.

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